

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

№3

ISSN: 2992-8982

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

2025

IQTISODIYOT&TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

Elektron nashr. 684 sahifa.

E'lon qilishga 2025-yil 11-martda ruxsat etildi.

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:

Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Maxmudov Nosir, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xajiyev Baxtiyor Dushaboyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), professor
Ali Konak (Ali Ko'nak), iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor (Turkiya)
Cham Tat Huei, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD), professor (Malayziya)
Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldixo'ja o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dots.
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, O'z.Respub. Bosh prokuraturasi boshqarma boshlig'i o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farkhod, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Bosh prokuraturasi IJQKD boshlig'i
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), katta o'qituvchi
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), v.b. dots.
Djudi Smetana, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Krissi Lyuis, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi (Moskva)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD) (Turkiya)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon o'g'li, TDIU ITI departamenti rahbari
Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o'g'li, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Editorial board:

- Salimov Okil Umrzokovich**, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjavevich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Rae Kwon Chung, South Korea, Honorary Professor at TSUE, Nobel Prize Laureate
Osman Mesten, Member of the Turkish Parliament, Head of the Turkey–Uzbekistan Friendship Society
Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhridinovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Siddikova Sadokat Gafforovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences
Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Makhmudov Nosir, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Professor
Slizovskiy Dmitriy Yegorovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abduganiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khajiyev Bakhtiyor Dushaboyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khakimov Nazar Khakimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Professor
Ali Konak, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor (Turkey)
Cham Tat Huei, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)
Foziljonov Ibrokhimjon Sotvoldikhoja ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Head of Department, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan
Ochilov Farkhod, Head of DCEC, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan
Buzrukkhonov Sarvarkhon Munavvarkhonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences
Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Technical Sciences, Senior Lecturer
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Acting Associate Professor
Judi Smetana, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Chrissy Lewis, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, Candidate of Economic Sciences (Moscow)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) (Turkey)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhmatjon ugli, Head of the Department of Scientific Research and Innovations, TSUE
Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli, Senior lecturer at TSUI

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Aliyev Bekdavlal Aliyevich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, katta o'qituvchi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, mustaqil tadqiqotchi

Board of Experts:

Berkinov Bazarbay, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Pulatov Bakhtiyor Alimovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Aliyev Bekdavlal Aliyevich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Rustamov Ilkhomiddin, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Khakimov Ziyodulla Akhmadovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics
Gafurov Doniyor Orifovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogy
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Tukhtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Khamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarimovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Yakhshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, Senior Lecturer
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, Independent Researcher

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

Improving the efficiency of investment activity in oil and gas enterprises.....	24
Raxmatova M.G., G'ofurov Sh.N.	
Organization of control and evaluation of effectiveness in international companies.....	30
Nasimov Bakhtiyor Vasiyevich	
Xalqaro standartlarning korxonaga eksportini oshishidagi ahamiyati.....	35
Sobitov Diyor Abbralxonovich	
Erkin iqtisodiy zonalar boshqaruvining tashkiliy tuzilmasini takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	40
Ataismatov Iqboljon Zumratjonovich	
Xorazm viloyatida turizm infratuzilmasini innovatsion rivojlantirish ko'rsatkichlarini ekonometrik modellashtirish va prognozlashtirishning ba'zi masalari.....	46
Jumaniyazova Ro'za Quvondiq qizi	
Tijorat banklarining moliyaviy barqarorligini mustahkamlash.....	60
Rasulov Muxammad Bobur Fazliddin o'g'li	
Economic analysis of investment activity of enterprises.....	66
Shermatov Akhror Abduhakimovich	
Kichik biznesni rivojlantirishda innovatsion faoliyatni moliyalashtirish yo'nalishlari.....	72
Z. Rahimova	
Влияние углеродного следа на экологическую устойчивость узбекистана.....	76
Саттарова Барно Шухратовна	
Moliya bozori dastaklari orqali xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb etish modellarining uslubiy asoslari.....	84
Ibragimov G'anijon G'ayratovich	
Maqdsadli tushumlarning audit obyekti sifatidagi tasnifi va tavsifi.....	90
Ne'matov Oybek Ismatullayevich, Qambarov Abduazizbek	
Bank majburiyatlari tushunchasi, uning mazmuni va mohiyati.....	96
Muminova Parvina Ilhom qizi	
Sanoat korxonalariga berilayotgan soliq imtiyozlari ma'murchiligini ta'minlash borasida amalga oshirilayotgan ishlar samaradorligi.....	100
Turabov Ulug'bek Olimjonovich	
Tur operatorlari va sayohat agentliklarida xarajatlar va foyda tahlili va uning turlari.....	106
Taniyev Ahmadjon Bahromovich	
O'zbekistonda kredit bozorini rivojlantirish istiqbollari.....	113
Salimov Burxon Abubakirovich	
Social media marketing as a key strategy in modern business.....	125
Najimova Bakhtigul Abdilkasim qizi	
O'zbekistonda yashil mahsulotlar eksportini rivojlantirish orqali barqaror iqtisodiy o'sish va xalqaro integratsiyani ta'minlash.....	129
Radjabov Bunyod Abduxalilovich	
Оценка и управление рисками в проектах строительства энергетических объектов.....	136
Махматкулов Жамшед Бахтиёрович	
Iqtisodiyotda ko'chmas mulk bozori hamda uning xususiyatlari.....	140
Ibragimov Qobil To'xtamishovich, Raimkulov Sherali O'rozdavlatovich, G'ffarov Husayn Aliyor o'g'li, Ismoilov Davronjon Ilxomjon o'g'li, Tashpulatova Shaxnoza Tursunpulatovna	
Ekologik turizmning ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy ta'siri va uni rivojlantirish istiqbollari (Jizzax viloyati misolida).....	144
Isomiddinov Sherzod Sirojiddin o'g'li	
Ways to improve personnel policy in improving the quality of financial services provided by financial institutions.....	148
Ergashev Umidjon Ibragimovich	
Qo'shilgan qiymat solig'ining budjet daromadlarini shakllantirishdagi ahamiyati.....	152
Djabbarov Anvar Muxammadsaliyevich	

Tadbirkorlik subyektlarining barqarorlik reytingini aniqlash va ulardan samarali foydalanish yo'llari	157
Abdullayev Zafarbek Safibullayevich	
Tovar-moddiy zaxiralar auditini tashkil qilish masalalari	164
Turmanqulov Norpo'lat Sa'dullayevich, Botirov Lazizbek Botirovich	
O'zbekiston tijorat banklari faoliyatida aktivlar daromadligini oshirish masalalari.....	168
Saxibjonov Muzaffar Salijanovich	
Organization of control and evaluation of effectiveness in international companies.....	174
Nasimov Bakhtiyor Vasiyevich	
Strategic growth of global companies in contemporary environments.....	179
Djurabaev Otabek Djurabayevich	
Directions for management of the tax system.....	184
Sharokhmatov Abdurakhim Abdulamitovich	
Davlat korxonalarida moliyaviy samaradorlik va uni boshqarish tizimini takomillashtirish yo'nalishlari.....	188
Qarshiyev Nodirbek Olim o'g'li	
Проблемы, модели и методы оптимизации управления товарными запасами	193
Бабаджанов Шопулат Шомашрабович	
Literature review: the significance of digitization to management credit activity of commercial banks	200
Jo'rayev Eldor Berdibekovich	
O'zbekiston Respublikasining davlat budjeti.....	205
Ajibaeva Raiya Maxsudovna	
Yashil iqtisodiyot kontsepsiyasining shakillanishi, taraqqiyot bosqichlari va uning dolzarbligi.....	212
Kodirov Javlonbek Nematullayevich	
Bank plastik kartalari orqali masofaviy xizmatlarni takomillashtirish.....	219
Abdullayeva Dildora Qudratovna, Abdullayev Baxodirjon Valijon o'g'li, Almuratova Nurliolmasoy Naim qizi	
O'zbekistonda iqtisodiy o'sishni ekonometrik modellashtirish	223
Shamsiyeva Feruza Muratxodjayevna	
Mahalla faoliyati ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy ko'rsatkichlarini tahlil qilishning nazariy asoslari.....	232
Aliqulov Ravshan Shodiyor o'g'li	
O'zbekistonda lizing bozori tahlili.....	237
Boyev Bekzodjon Jo'raqul o'g'li, Shavkatov Behruz Rustam o'g'li	
Chakana savdoni rivojlantirishning mintaqaviy xususiyatlari	241
Ismoilov Shohjahon O'tkir o'g'li	
O'zbekistonda tibbiy xizmatlarning rivojlanish tendensiyalari, tarkibiy tuzilish tasnifi va marketing segmentlari	244
Axmedov Zafarjon A'zamovich	
Мировой опыт и перспективы развития свободно экономических зон в Республике Узбекистан.....	250
Кадирова Истора Кадирова	
Перспективы реформирования налоговой системы Республики Узбекистан в условиях глобализации.....	254
Буранова Лола Вахобовна, Садиков Искандар Гайратович	
O'zbekiston 2030 strategiyasi – islohotlar tizimligida ipoteka kreditining dolzarbligi.....	263
A'zamxo'jayeva Nihola	
O'zbekistonda sug'urta mexanizmlarini rivojlantirish istiqbollari	267
Shoraximova Zilola Nosirdjanovna	
Biologiya va tibbiyotda matematik statistika	271
Voxidov Alikul Melitoshevich	
Viloyatda chorvachilik mahsulotlarini o'tgan yilga nisbatan o'zgarishi.....	283
Azimov Allaberdin O'rinovich, Begaliyeva Madina Abdusamatovna	
Servis korxonalarida mobil ilovalar yordamida interaktiv xizmatlar yaratish	289
Ne'matov Nizom Ismatullayevich	
Oziq-ovqat ta'minot zanjiri tushunchasi va uning zamonaviy tendensiyalari.....	293
Nazarova A.N	

Влияние искусственного интеллекта при разработке стратегических программ на экономическое развитие страны.....	300
Каримова Нуржахон Олим кизи	
Kichik va o'rta biznesda moliyaviy menejment: muammolar va yechimlar	306
Saidvaliyeva Nigora Ziyodillayevna	
Теоретико-правовая характеристика экономических отношений	313
Фарход Махмудович Тиркашев, Исломжон Жамшедович Жамшедов	
Cash flow reporting in Uzbekistan: national accounting standards and international standards application	318
Ochilov Ilyos Keldiyorovich	
Tadbirkorlik salohiyatini rivojlantirishning ustuvor yo'nalishlari va takomillashtirish mexanizmlari	324
Baxtiyor Xabibullayev Abdulvoxid o'g'li	
Получение долгосрочного кредита и определение его размера для привлечения лизинга	330
Латипова Шахноза Махмудовна	
Ko'chmas mulk solig'ining ko'chmas mulk bozori tendensiyalariga ta'siri	335
To'lakov Ulug'bek Toshmamatovich	
Rivojlangan mamlakatlarning davlat qarzi va uni boshqarishdagi tajribasini tahlil qilishga ilmiy yondashuv	343
Suynov Dilmurod Xolmuradovich, Abdurahmonova Feruzabonu	
Эффективный инновационный менеджмент в системе здравоохранения Республики Узбекистан.....	353
Абдурахманов З.М.	
Islom moliyasining O'zbekistondagi o'rni va O'zbekiston Respublikasining islomiy tashkilotlar va banklar bilan aloqasi	356
Otajonova Charosxon Polvonquli qizi, Elboyev Otajon Polvonquliyevich	
Tadbirkorlik subyektlarida innovatsion faoliyatni rivojlantirishning ustuvor yo'nalishlari.....	361
Oxunjonova Madina Isoqjonovna	
Основные задачи обеспечения цифровой информационной безопасности в образовательном процессе	365
Иззатилла Пулатов Кудратиллаевич	
Tijorat banklarida komplaens nazoratni takomillashtirish.....	373
Muminova Marguba Mamirkulovna	
Kichik biznes uchun soliq imtiyozlari va ularning samaradorligi.....	378
Sarvar Ochilov	
Xalqaro moliyaviy tashkilotlarning davlat iqtisodiy rivojlanishidagi o'rni	387
Raxmonova Dildora Ergash qizi	
O'zbekiston Respublikasida kreditning iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishdagi o'rni	395
Eshqobulova Charos O'roq qizi	
Mintaqa sanoat korxonalarida investitsiya jarayonlari rivojlanish tendensiyasining statistik tahlili.....	399
Quvatova Gulzoda Faxriddin qizi	
Natijalarga yo'naltirilgan budjetlashtirish samarali budjet menejmentining omili sifatida	403
N. Sheraliev	
O'zbekistonda kichik biznesning rivojlanish tendensiyalari va istiqbollari	408
Salayev Jasurbek Komilovich	
Features and prospects for the development of digital marketing in Uzbekistan.....	414
Musayeva Shoirazimovna	
Анализ динамики импорта узбекистана в 2017–2024 годах с учетом индекса сложности продукции (PCI)	418
Жабборова Нодира Холмурод кизи	
O'zbekistonning kredit riskini baholash: iqtisodiy barqarorlik va xavf omillari tahlili	422
Hakimov Hakimjon Abdullo o'g'li	
Investitsion jozibadorlikni oshirish – korxonalarining raqobatbardoshligini oshirishning muhim shartidir	426
Karimova Dilafuz Sadirdin qizi	

Sanoat korxonalarida innovatsion faollikni oshirish omillari.....	431
Qo'ziyev Shodiyor Qilichboy o'g'li, Xakimov Javohir Hamza o'g'li, Turganbaev Nursultan Bayram o'g'li, Masharipov Rasulbek Jo'rabekovich, Xasanov Ruslan Raxmatovich, Nurullayev Jasurbek Davronbekovich	
Теоретические основы формирования понятия «финансовая стабильность».....	437
Алиева Сусанна Сейрановна	
Developing the labor market and strategies for reducing unemployment.....	442
Tojiyeva Muhabbatxon Mansurjon qizi, Elmurodov Mukhammadkodir Nurmuhammad	
Iqlim o'zgarishi sharoitida raqamli texnologiyalar orqali qishloq xo'jaligida samaradorlikni oshirish yo'llari.....	450
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, Ochilov Ilhom Sayitqulovich, Sayfullayeva Ruxshona Farrux qizi	
To'g'ridan-to'g'ri xorijiy investitsiyalarning sanoatni rivojlantirishdagi roli.....	458
Samijonov Musobek G'ayratjon o'g'li	
Ishlab chiqarish korxonalarida risklarni boshqarishning asosiy yo'nalishlari va rivojlanish istiqbollari.....	466
Muxitdinov Shuhrat Ziyavitdinovich	
Ovqatlanish xizmatlarini rivojlantirishning tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizmlaridan foydalanish va samaradorligini oshirishning asosiy yo'nalishlari.....	470
Ravshanov Zaxiriddin Ibragimovich	
Ta'lim jarayonida sun'iy intellektdan foydalanishning ahamiyati.....	477
Safayeva Dilafuz Ruzmatovna, Karimov Abrorjon Shavkat o'g'li	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarini xarajatlarini rejalashtirish va moliyalashtirish: amaldagi holat tahlili.....	482
Bauyetdinov M.J., Medetbayeva D.T	
Tijorat banklarida foiz risklarini baholash va boshqarish.....	487
Karimov Mardon Akram o'g'li	
Zamonaviy sharoitda bank innovatsiyalaridan foydalanishning istiqbolli yo'nalishlari.....	494
Xodjimamedov Akmal Ashurovich	
A local perspective on sustainable supply chain management in Uzbekistan.....	501
Oybek Rafukjonkhajiev	
Raqamli texnologiyalar orqali sug'urta kompaniyalar marketing faoliyatini takomillashtirish.....	505
Rashidova Dildora Rasul qizi	
O'zbekistonning strategik rivojlanish davrida investitsiyalarning o'rni.....	511
Akbaraliyeva Aziza Maxmadali qizi	
O'zbekiston media bozori: rivojlanishi va afzalliklari.....	516
Qodirov Obidjon Olim o'g'li	
Порядок учета скидок в бухгалтерском учете на основе МСФО.....	520
Камолова Феруза Кахрамоновна	
Tijorat banklari transformatsiyasini amalga oshirishda qimmatli qog'ozlar bozorida foydalanishning xorijiy tajribasi.....	525
Bobur Abrorovich Yusupov	
Neft va gaz sanoati korxonalarini resurslardan samarali foydalanishning xorijiy tajribalari tahlili.....	533
Sonayev Sanjar Nurmatovich	
Оценка социально-экономического воздействия железнодорожных проектов.....	539
Хужаяров Бекзод Баходир угли	
Rivojlanayotgan mamlakatlarda islom mikromoliyalashning innovatsion mexanizmlari va xalqaro tajriba.....	544
Sharipova Maxliyoxon Baxtiyor qizi	
Iqtisodiy samaradorlik tushunchasining ilmiy- nazariy tahlili.....	548
Ibragimov Zukhriddin Sayfutdinovich	
Ipoteka kreditlarini moliyalashtirishda banklarning o'rni va istiqbollari.....	552
Muhitdinov Ulug'bek Diyorovich	
Mintaqaviy mehnat bozorini shakllanishining shart-sharoitlari, omillari, o'ziga xos xususiyatlari va prinsiplari.....	556
Amonov Navro'zxon Saloxiddin o'g'li	
Development of digital marketing for sustainable tourism development in Uzbekistan.....	560
Nasibabonu Abdurakhmonovna Akramova	

Kichik biznes subyektlarining raqobatbardoshligini oshirishga qaratilgan innovatsion yondashuvlar	565
Ibragimov Ulmas	
Tijorat banklarining moliyaviy xavfsizligini ta'minlashning dolzarb masalalari	569
Akbarov Behzodxon Ulug'bek o'g'li	
Amerika qo'shma shtatlarida federal zaxira tizimi tomonidan amalga oshirilgan noan'anaviy pul-kredit siyosati.....	574
Djumonov Dilshod Safaroliyevich	
Intellectual mulkning ishlab chiqarishdagi ahamiyati	581
Farhod Mahmudovich Tirkashyev, Azizbek Umid o'g'li Abduvaliyev	
Tijorat banklari moliyaviy barqarorligini baholashning xorijiy davlatlar tajribasi	585
Sattarova Gulshan Muxiddinovna	
Qimmatli qog'ozlar bozorida moliyaviy xavfsizlik: investorlar misolida.....	589
Boysunov Jamshid Baxriddin ug'li	
Amaliy-ilmiy tadqiqotlarning mazmuni, asosiy maqsadlari va qo'llanilish shakllari.....	593
Raupov Jamshid Rashidovich, Kaxramonov Zafar Kaxramonovich	
Tijorat banklarida korporativ boshqaruvni takomillashtirishning dolzarb masalalari.....	597
Ergashev Olim Kenjayevich	
Islom darchalari asosida moliyalashtirishni joriy etish istiqbollari	602
Gulyamova Shaxnoza Gafurdjanovna	
Влияние финансовых технологий на трансформацию страхового рынка.....	606
Тангирбердиева Гулчехра Рахимжановна	
Tadbirkorlik faoliyatini rivojlanishida mamlakatimiz iqtisodiyotini holati tahlili	611
Muradova Maxliyoxon Ravshanovna	
Foreign experience in the formation of banking assets in improving the efficiency of the activities of commercial banks.....	615
Ibrohimov Davronbek Muhammadi ogli	
Роль и значение экономического потенциала в формировании стратегии регионов Узбекистана.....	628
Абдалова З.Т.	
Перспективы развития торговых отношений между Китаем и Узбекистаном.....	634
Фазлиддинова Шахруза студентка, Расулев Дильмурод Мирза-Ахмедович	
Korxonalarda moliyaviy instrumentlarning hisobi va audit masalalarini rivojlantirish	640
Maxmudov Saidjamol Kadirjanovich	
Barqaror ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlanishning ilmiy-nazariy asoslari.....	647
Rajabov Alibek	
Digital technologies as a driver for the development of mice tourism in Uzbekistan	654
Ilkhomova Gulnoza Zaynitdin qizi	
Tadbirkorlik subyektlarining tashqi savdo faoliyati bojxona reytingini aniqlash va baholashning iqtisodiy ahamiyati.....	661
Azizov Sherzod Uktamovich, Mamarajabov Abdisamad Saidmurot o'g'li	
Kichik biznes va tadbirkorlik subyektlari	666
Shodiyev To'liqin Oltiboy o'g'li	
Sanoat korxonalari rivojlanishining atrof-muhitga ta'sirini baholashda esg tamoyillarini qo'llash imkoniyatlari va istiqbollari	671
Turg'unov Jasurbek Alimardon o'g'li	
Museum collection management and new technology	677
Ibroximova Aziza Abbasovna	

MUSEUM COLLECTION MANAGEMENT AND NEW TECHNOLOGY

Ibroximova Aziza Abbasovna

Westminster International University in Tashkent

Phd student

Abstract: This paper presents an outline of the uses of new technology in the museum and heritage sector for the collection management, access to the collection and the interpretation of the collection. Despite the ever-increasing attention paid to museums, the storage plays a marginal role: an invisible resource, whose potential is often little explored and/or valued. What is the situation of archaeological museum storage in Uzbekistan? Some reflections are presented here, rising from the results of a recent statistical survey conducted within the IVLP Impact Award Project by the writer during her research project on the Protection and Preservation of Archaeological Collections, in collaboration with the State museums of Uzbekistan and Research Institutions. Results of the survey conducted within the IVLP Impact Award Project. The study emphasizes the importance of digital inventory and cataloging for protection and preservation.

Key words: cataloging, inventory, technology, museums, collection, management, digital cataloging system, virtual reality technology, multimedia, mobile technology.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada muzey va meros sektorida kolleksiyani boshqarish, kolleksiyaga kirish va kolleksiyani talqin qilish uchun yangi texnologiyalardan foydalanishning tavsifi keltirilgan. Muzeylarga tobora ortib borayotgan e'tiborga qaramay, saqlash marginal rol o'ynaydi: ko'rinmas resurs, uning salohiyati ko'pincha kam o'rganiladi va / yoki qadrlanadi. O'zbekistonda arxeologiya muzeylarini saqlash holati qanday? Bu yerda yozuvchining O'zbekiston davlat muzeylari va ilmiy-tadqiqot muassasalari bilan hamkorlikda arxeologik kolleksiyalarni muhofaza qilish va saqlash bo'yicha tadqiqot loyihasi davomida IVLP Impact Award loyihasi doirasida yaqinda o'tkazilgan statistik so'rov natijalaridan kelib chiqqan holda ba'zi fikrlar keltirilgan. IVLP Impact Award loyihasi doirasida o'tkazilgan so'rov natijalari. Tadqiqot himoya va saqlash uchun raqamli inventarizatsiya va kataloglashtirishning muhimligini ta'kidlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: kataloglashtirish, inventarizatsiya, texnologiya, muzeylar, kolleksiya, boshqaruv, raqamli kataloglash tizimi, virtual reallik texnologiyasi, multimedia, mobil texnologiyalar.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлен обзор использования новых технологий в музейном и историко-культурном секторе для управления коллекциями, доступа к коллекциям и интерпретации коллекций. Несмотря на постоянно растущее внимание, уделяемое музеям, хранилище играет второстепенную роль: невидимый ресурс, потенциал которого часто мало изучен и/или оценен. Какова ситуация с археологическим музейным хранилищем в Узбекистане? Здесь представлены некоторые размышления, вытекающие из результатов недавнего статистического исследования, проведенного в рамках проекта премии IVLP Impact Award автором в ходе ее исследовательского проекта по защите и сохранению археологических коллекций в сотрудничестве с государственными музеями Узбекистана и научно-исследовательскими институтами. Результаты исследования, проведенного в рамках проекта премии IVLP Impact Award. В исследовании подчеркивается важность цифровой инвентаризации и каталогизации для защиты и сохранения.

Ключевые слова: каталогизация, инвентаризация, технология, музеи, коллекция, управление, система цифровой каталогизации, технология виртуальной реальности, мультимедиа, мобильные технологии.

INTRODUCTION

A museum is a permanent, non-commercial organization dedicated to serving society and advancing its progress. It welcomes the public, actively acquiring, preserving, studying, interpreting, and showcasing artifacts and other tangible records of human life and the environment. These activities support education, research, and public appreciation[1].

Museums have an important duty to develop their educational role and attract wider audiences from the communities, localities, or groups they serve. Interaction with the constituent community and the promotion of its heritage is an integral part of the museum's educational role [2]. By using new technology, museums are fulfilling their commitment to society by attracting visitors, expanding access for the public, and promoting the heritage sector [3].

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE TOPIC

Museums, as cultural promoters and heritage-preserving institutions, are constantly faced with the challenges of the modern world. They seek to apply innovative technologies to meet the needs of visitors and to present their collections in a comfortable and engaging manner to a wide audience. Modern technologies play a significant role in this process, providing new opportunities for organizing museum activities and enriching the visitor's experience [4].

Various advanced technologies are now widely implemented in museums and cultural heritage institutions globally, especially in developed regions. These innovations have transformed the operations and visitor experiences of museums and galleries in ways that were unimaginable a decade ago. Emerging technologies create exciting opportunities to significantly enrich visitor engagement while also improving the management, accessibility, and interpretation of collections.

Museums began using automation technology in the early 1960s [5]. Before the introduction of information technology, museums used various manual cataloguing systems. For example, multiple card catalogues were employed to create cross-referenced indices to handle large volumes of information. Drawing and photography were also used to document museum collections. Often, cataloguing took place outside the museum, for example, at a university or a state agency.

Dr. Jack Heller, a computer science professor at SUNY, significantly advanced museum technology in 1967 by founding the Museum Computer Network (MCN). A year later, in 1968, MCN collaborated with IBM to host a groundbreaking conference exploring computer applications in museum contexts. By 1969, David Vance had launched a notable standardization initiative with twelve art museums, marking a pivotal moment in organizing museum information. The advent of affordable desktop computers and enhanced storage devices in the early 1980s further propelled technological progress. This movement reached a milestone in 1984 when the Smithsonian adopted personal computers (PCs), establishing a foundation for modern museum informatics.

Museums around the globe began going online in response to the coronavirus crisis. The world's first fully interactive virtual museum launched on September 4. The Virtual Online Museum of Art (VOMA) presents "exquisitely curated" exhibitions and is a free, fully immersive museum that anyone, anywhere in the world, can visit. The experience aims to be as authentic as visiting a physical museum. VOMA features classic and contemporary artworks that are free to view. As for the technology involved, VOMA was built using the latest virtual reality (VR) gaming technology, CGI, and network computing [6].

Collections are the defining attribute of museums. Their management is at the heart of every museum's operations. Proper documentation and care are the fundamental criteria of a well-managed museum, as the institution's ability to provide meaningful experiences for the public—now and in the future—depends on its collections and the information about them [7].

New technology in museums can be discussed under several categories: multimedia, new media, mobile technology, web and internet, computer devices, and digital platforms.

Multimedia, in general terms, serves both as a tool for interpretation and for the documentation and delivery of content. Within museums, multimedia has two key roles: as a communication tool and as a documentation tool. As a communication tool, multimedia helps structure and interpret knowledge about resources, artefacts, and collections. As a documentation tool, it helps in creating databases and systems that capture and preserve multi-layered information. It is particularly useful for interpreting collections that are not physically accessible (e.g. stored items), or for reaching virtual visitors who are geographically distant.

New media generally encompasses digital technologies and electronic multimedia that invite interactive engagement. It broadly refers to innovative communication channels like web-based platforms, email, digital audio and video formats (including videoconferencing and video-on-demand), interactive multimedia, digital television, mobile communication devices, and electronic publishing[3]. For instance, at the 2018 exhibition titled "Blue and White Porcelain – A Symbol of the Greatness of the Silk Road," a multimedia presentation showcased all items, even those not physically displayed, enhancing the audience's access to the full collection.

As people increasingly incorporate digital technology into their daily lives, devices are becoming indispensable. Museums have responded with a multitude of digital applications. Over the past decade, digital technology has become a watchword for museum planners. Japan holds the enviable position of often being at the forefront of technological development [8, 4]. The growth of media channels has significantly supported the dissemination of museum collections worldwide.

Interactive multimedia combines text, graphics, sound, animation, video, and interactivity into a single medium. Its introduction in museums helps facilitate communication between systems and users. For example, interactive systems require input from the audience, encouraging greater visitor engagement.

Multimedia kiosk installations have rapidly increased in recent years. Today, interactive multimedia exhibits are essential features of new museum galleries. This technology is simple, cost-effective, and requires minimal

technical expertise. For instance, in 2014, the State Museum of the History of Uzbekistan installed information kiosks in its new exhibition “Independent Uzbekistan”, providing comprehensive information about the nation’s history since 1991.

Mobile technology enriches the museum experience by offering convenient access to detailed information about collections. It also provides valuable support for visitors with disabilities; for instance, pressing a button can deliver audio interpretations or unlock additional content. This approach has been effectively implemented in numerous museums across Japan[9].

Web and internet technologies offer a fast, cost-effective, and convenient way to share information globally. Through websites, museums improve accessibility for researchers and educators and expand public engagement. According to ICOM guidelines, the internet provides three major functions for museums: (1) person-to-person service via email, (2) group communication through mailing lists and discussion forums, and (3) access to information resources via electronic document servers. Websites allow users to browse collections from anywhere in the world and explore virtual tours and online exhibitions. The World Wide Web (WWW) is increasingly vital for heritage attractions and museums, offering new channels of communication and effective tools for marketing destinations and experiences [10].

Collection documentation and data integration involve more than simple registration or cataloguing. It includes managing the location and movement of all objects. Computers assist in documenting objects through data entry, image capture, data storage, and cataloguing. A Digital Asset Management (DAM) system can organize archives and collections, offering a robust solution to protect, manage, and share cultural heritage. Integrating DAM systems allows museums to streamline operations while preserving their priceless assets [11]. These systems support long-term digital file accessibility and enable virtual exhibits that bring history to life. DAM is essential for sustainability, helping museums innovate, collaborate globally, and engage wider audiences.

Museums are treasure troves of cultural artifacts, but managing and accessing these treasures poses challenges. Digital asset management systems solve this by organizing and streamlining digital collection handling. Whether improving accessibility or ensuring compliance, DAM systems are critical for modern museum operations. These solutions help manage organization, provenance, sharing, usability, preservation, and distribution vital for sustainability in the 21st century [12].

A museum cannot survive without preserving its works. The storage facilities essential for preservation often receive little attention, despite their critical role. Storage remains a largely invisible resource to the public, yet it holds immense potential. Recognizing storage areas alongside exhibition spaces as dynamic, multifaceted components of museum operations is essential. This is particularly true for archaeological material storages, which face continuous and exponential growth. Rethinking the role of storage is now a fundamental challenge for museums striving to remain relevant as centers of knowledge serving the community [13].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Archaeological museum storage remains a critical component in the protection and long-term preservation of cultural heritage. However, it faces persistent challenges, especially in terms of capacity, environmental control, and access to modern technologies. Issues such as overcrowded storage rooms, insufficient documentation, inadequate preservation conditions, and a lack of digitization tools continue to hinder the efficient management of archaeological collections.

In 2023, a statistical survey was conducted by the author as part of the Protection and Preservation of Archaeological Collections project, in collaboration with the State Museum of the History of Uzbekistan, local museums, and research institutions. The survey was carried out within the framework of the IVLP Impact Award Project.

In August 2023, a comprehensive questionnaire was successfully prepared and distributed to central museums in Tashkent, Samarkand, and Bukhara. The aim of the survey was to create an updated and thorough mapping of the archaeological museum heritage in these key cities. The project recorded notable progress in the following key areas:

- a) Inventory and Cataloging – Evaluation of existing documentation systems, data completeness, and accuracy of inventory records;
- b) Preservation – Assessment of safety measures, storage environments, and risk parameter controls, such as humidity, temperature, lighting, and pest prevention;
- c) Digitalization – Analysis of the involvement of museums in digitizing their collections and the integration of information technologies for long-term access and sustainability.

These findings have provided a valuable foundation for future initiatives aimed at strengthening archaeological collection management in Uzbekistan and fostering international collaboration on cultural heritage preservation.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Based on the survey responses from participating museums, key intervention areas have been identified.

a) Inventory and Cataloguing

Museums reported the total number of items in their collections (Figure 1), as well as the specific number of archaeological objects included (Figure 2), in relation to their overall inventory.

Figure 1: State and non-state archaeological museums participating in the survey: a total number of stored items [14].

Figure 2: Number of archaeological collection (pieces)[14].

The inventory process certifies the existence of an item, assigning it a record number, essential identification data, provenance history, and economic value. It is the primary and indispensable step to ensure the existence, protection, and preservation of an object. If an item is not inventoried, it technically does not exist within the museum's records. Without proper documentation, museums cannot accurately track the items in their collections where they are placed, how they are stored, and the conditions they are kept under. This results in complications, including potential financial losses in the event of theft, damage, or loss. Although these are average values, the percentage of catalogued items in most museums remains low (see Figure 3).

Figure 3: Percentage of inventoried and catalogued items (from 0% to 100%) [14].

b) Preservation: Safety and Control of Risk Parameters

The tangible components of cultural heritage such as artifacts and historical sites serve as enduring records of human history, reflecting our ancestors' achievements, perspectives, and creative expressions.

These materials are not only one-of-a-kind and non-replaceable, but they are also inherently fragile. Heritage institutions shoulder the profound responsibility of preserving these treasures while ensuring public access, fostering a deeper understanding of our collective past. Achieving this involves developing and executing strategies to mitigate risks to the cultural assets under their care [15].

Heritage professionals frequently face challenging decisions about resource allocation to safeguard collections, buildings, monuments, and sites. This may entail choosing among various protective measures, including enhancing security to deter theft and vandalism, improving building maintenance to prevent water damage, installing climate control systems in storage areas, utilizing specialized pest management, upgrading fire detection and suppression systems, creating disaster preparedness and response plans, constructing additional storage facilities, investing in conservation-grade materials, or expanding conservation and restoration efforts [16].

The survey results were analyzed with consideration for conservation, preservation, and management concerns. Several key problems were identified. According to the data, 80% of the surveyed respondents reported that their archaeological collections are kept under appropriate temperature and relative humidity conditions. However, 20% indicated that their collections are stored in substandard conditions. These figures suggest that a significant portion of museum collections remain vulnerable due to inadequate storage environments.

Further analysis conducted during the survey identified several causes for improper storage (Figure 4). These included:

- Non-compliance of the storage facilities with standard requirements (66% of respondents);
- Lack of proper technology (17%);
- Insufficient financial resources (17%).

These findings point to critical structural and financial deficiencies in heritage preservation infrastructure, underscoring the need for increased investment, improved facilities, and broader technical support.

Figure 4: Percentage of problems regarding to storage (from 0% to 100%) [14].

c) *Involvement in the digitalization;*

As technology has rapidly advanced, so have many museums endeavored to employ newly available methods of organization, presentation, and education to their exhibits. Although digital methods of documenting museum specimens for collections based scientific research have been less explored, they are certainly no less imperative. The two main functions of museums are not mutually exclusive and digitizing museum specimens and their associated data can only serve to propagate both: cultivating education and preserving cultural history [17]. Over the past decade, many museums have taken strides to incorporate digital methods of documenting their collections [18]. It has proven a blanket term that has been used to describe anything from computer data input (transcribing information from catalog cards into an electronic database), to digital photography to the creation of virtual reality systems and everything in between. Electronic collections and archive databases are quite common in museums. Entries for specimens are not always complete (containing data from all sources) and as a result strides to fill in the blanks and include digital images and document scans are being undertaken. These kinds of digital projects: data migration, imaging, and georeferencing, are essential steps in the process of building comprehensive digital databases. Digital documentation can be applied to organize collections and forge new frontiers in research [19].

The inventory process is a critical step in confirming the existence of an artifact or item, as it assigns a record number along with essential identifying information, provenance, and economic value. This procedure forms the foundation for ensuring the protection, preservation, and proper management of cultural assets. Without inventory documentation, an item effectively remains “invisible” in terms of legal and economic standing, including its recognition within the state’s patrimony. Furthermore, incomplete or absent documentation makes it difficult for museums to maintain accurate knowledge of what their collections contain, where items are

stored, and how they are preserved, leading to potential economic consequences in cases of theft, damage, or loss. The survey results show that a considerable number of museums have adopted digital inventory systems to address these challenges.

Figure 5: Type of used inventory (from 0% to 100%) [14].

During the survey involvement in the digitalization of the museum collection has been identified. Questions including “Is the museum actively involved in the digitalization?”, “What percentage of your permanent archaeological collection has been digitized?” were asked, the following results were obtained. According to results obtained more than a half of the museums (80% out of 100%) are involved in collection digitalization, and smaller number of museums (20% out of 100%) are not actively involved in (Figure 5). On the base of the given answers the reason of the problems of digitization of archaeological items were the lack of relevant personnel and the weak qualifications of researchers.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Through a detailed statistical survey, Uzbekistan’s museums have been able to construct a thorough and current mapping of their archaeological collections that are not currently on display.

The findings, though summarized briefly here, are significant and highly relevant to the current historical context, providing a clear depiction of the state of museums today. The survey underscores that implementing proper inventory and cataloguing procedures is a top priority—an essential foundation for all related tasks, including protecting collections against damage or theft, ensuring conservation, improving accessibility, and enhancing overall value. Adopting computerized inventory management systems is critical. Such systems simplify documentation, improve process traceability, optimize resource usage, reduce management time and costs, enhance overall quality, and ensure broad accessibility and smooth data sharing.

Statistical research indicates that integrating digital technology into inventory and cataloging processes is essential, serving as a foundational step for storage and all preservation-related activities. Such interventions enhance both protection and accessibility. To achieve this, cultural heritage institutions and associated organizations must establish formal regulations for implementing a computerized system dedicated to preserving ancestral and cultural heritage. This system would streamline documentation, enable better process management and oversight, elevate procedural quality, and promote broader use and distribution of information.

It is therefore crucial for cultural heritage institutions and associated organizations to establish guidelines for adopting a digital heritage preservation system. Such a system would streamline documentation, enhance process management and oversight, raise overall process quality, and facilitate broader accessibility and dissemination of information.

In summary, it’s essential to recognize that conservation and preservation challenges are highly complex. Addressing these issues demands a systematic approach, strategic planning at the national level, and the adoption of standardized criteria, methodologies, and common guidelines.

List of references used

1. ICOM. (2022). Definition by the 10th Extraordinary General Assembly of ICOM. Prague.
2. ICOM. (2013). ICOM Code of Ethics for Museums (22 p.).
3. Sikder, M. D. Z. (2008–2010). Museum, collection management and new technology. The Jahangirnagar Review, Part C, 20–21, 373–389.
4. Kultaşeva, N. D. (2024). Integratsiya informatsionnykh tekhnologiy v muzey: mirovoy opyt i perspektivy. New Concept of Museums: Integration of IT Technologies in the Activities of Museums. Republican Scientific and Practical Conference Collection, Tashkent, 17–22.
5. Walden, V. G. (2022). The memorial museum in the digital age (Chapter 1). Arts and Humanities, University of Sussex, 20–53. <http://reframe.sussex.ac.uk/reframe-books>

6. Bloolooop. (n.d.). Virtual Online Museum of Art (VOMA). Retrieved from <https://bloolooop.com/brands-ip/news/virtual-online-museum-art-voma>
7. Lord, B., & Lord, G. D. (1997). Collection management. In *The Manual of Museum Management* (267 p.). Altamira Press.
8. Manabe, M., & Laydens, L. (2007). Digital technology in Japanese museums. *Journal of Museum Education*, 31(1), 3–5.
9. Yumi, A. (2007). Brief pictorial description of new mobile technology used in the cultural institute in Japan. *Journal of Museum Education*, 32(1), 17–25.
10. Evans, J. A., & Starry, P. (1999). Portable computers & interactive multimedia: A new paradigm for interpreting museum collections. *Archives and Museum Informatics*, 113–126.
11. Aprimo. (n.d.). How digital asset management for museums preserves cultural heritage. Retrieved from <https://www.aprimo.com/blog/how-digital-asset-management-for-museums-preserves-cultural-heritage>
12. Miller, D. (n.d.). DAM and Collection Management System Administrator at Queensland Museum. Retrieved from <https://www.fotoware.com/blog/how-digital-asset-managment-helps-museums-streamline-operations>
13. Brunella, M. (2019). Museum archaeological collection storage: Reassessing needs and priorities. *Tafer Journal*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/333867761>
14. Author. (2023). Compiled by the author on the basis of a survey conducted as part of the study.
15. Aslan, Z. (n.d.). Regional Representative of ICCROM for the Arab States. Director of ICCROM-ATHAR Regional Conservation Centre in the U.A.E.
16. Canadian Conservation Institute. (2016). *A Guide to Risk Management of Cultural Heritage* (p. 116). Government of Canada, International Centre for the Study of the Preservation and Restoration of Cultural Property.
17. Graham, C. A. (2012). Applications of digitization to museum collections management, research, and accessibility (Master's thesis).
18. Library of Congress. (2002). *Preserving our digital heritage: Plan for the National Digital Information Infrastructure and Preservation Program* (p. 74).
19. Bates, K. T., Falkingham, P. L., Rarity, F., Hodgetts, D., Purslow, A., & Manning, P. L. (2010). Application of high-resolution laser scanning and photometric techniques to data acquisition, analysis, and interpretation in paleontology. *International Archives of Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences*, 38(5), 68–73.

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2025. № 3

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin. Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

EI.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: @iqtisodiyot_77

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, @iqtisodiyot_77 telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>